

Lost in translation: Unlocking planning's potential to harness social value from property development projects

Nagwa Kady, University of Amsterdam

Sara Özogul, University of Groningen

Tuna Taşan-Kok, University of Amsterdam

Abstract

Urban planning aims to safeguard public interests and establish norms and principles through spatial regulations to foster social value within communities. However, tools utilized by public planning institutions often fail to align with strategies employed by the property industry to enhance social value in urban development practices. We argue that social value is often lost in translation between public and private realms due to fragmentation at an institutional and project level, impeding effectively harnessing social value objectives. The property industry focuses on creating social value within specific projects but struggles to connect these efforts to broader public interests. Our research shows that public realms establish social value parameters, yet face challenges due to conflicting perceptions, reduced municipal influence, shifting roles in value implementation, and municipal passiveness. We move beyond dominating narratives of market-driven urban development and entrepreneurial governance arrangements to focus on the interplay between public and private sector actors involved in property development projects. By developing a framework tracing social value creation through development phases: perception, implementation, and operation, we unpack the materialisation of social value through municipal and property industry (inter)actions. Our findings demonstrate the untapped potential of social value for planners to realize societal benefits in property development processes, emphasizing the overlap of public-private interests.

Keywords

Social value, property development, urban planning, urban development

Corresponding Author: Nagwa Kady, Department of Geography, Planning and International Development, University of Amsterdam, The Netherlands, n.s.a.kady@uva.nl, ORCID: 0000-0003-2783-7268

Authors: Sara Özogul, Department of Spatial Planning and Environment, University of Groningen, The Netherlands, s.ozogul@rug.nl, ORCID: 0000-0002-9011-7995

Tuna Taşan-Kok, Department of Geography, Planning and International Development, University of Amsterdam, The Netherlands, m.t.tasankok@uva.nl, ORCID: 0000-0003-4902-6650

Introduction

The creation of social value is intrinsic to urban planning and development practices, encompassing the qualities associated with public interest that planning mechanisms strive to establish and protect. Social value generally attributes to the physical and non-physical social impacts and wider decision-making processes on people and places (Council, 2018; Shirazi et al., 2022; Social Value UK, 2023). In this line of thinking, it includes factors such as improving access to public spaces, promoting health and well-being, increasing social cohesion, or creating housing for all income classes. The creation of social value entails the relational coordination between actors in pursuance of generating added value (Caldwell et al., 2017; Chesbrough et al., 2018).

The emergence of entrepreneurial urban governance models and property-led urban planning approaches, which require close collaboration between public actors and private sector entities, significantly influences the framing of social value within spatial planning institutions. In recent years, there has been a notable surge in interest and involvement of property actors to engage with social value (Corfe & Pardoe, 2022; O’Roarty, 2022). This interest can be explained by the increased corporate social responsibilities that can be traced back to the early 20th century, with efforts by certain companies to address societal issues such as labour conditions and environmental impact. The property industry has been compelled to reconcile profit generation with social and environmental impact due to a combination of social movements, regulatory shifts, and evolving business ideologies. These developments, although still driven by profit, have enabled novel mechanisms for creating social value beyond financial gains while the property industry uses standards to ensure better outcomes for both the industry and society in the built environments they create (Raiden & King, 2022).

Given current developments in the property industry, the striking overlap between social value targets, and common ambitions of planners, social value can be identified as key to fostering collaboration between planners and property actors to unlock further societal benefits. The process of social value creation requires stakeholders’ ability to capture values generated by both parties during resource utilization, ensuring the attainment of social value outcomes (Chesbrough et al., 2018). Yet, the standards of social value creation in the property industry often do not align with the mechanisms in planning systems aimed at safeguarding the public interest.

Moving beyond prevalent discourses and perceptions surrounding property actors in planning scholarship, we undertake a comprehensive analysis of how social value translates from perceptions to practice from a planning perspective. We argue that it often fails to be effectively harnessed due to institutional fragmentation that impedes the capture of values during their translation between different realms. Focussing explicitly on the actions and interactions of municipal and property actors as key players in contemporary property

development practices, we unpack the complexities behind framing and translating social value in property development processes shaped by a fragmented institutional landscape.

Our theoretical contribution lies in the development of a novel framework that traces social value creation through three stages: perception, implementation, and operation. By examining the dynamic interplay between public and private actors, we reveal how institutional fragmentation hinders the effective realization of social value. Moving beyond traditional market-driven development narratives, we explore how social value is conceptualized, negotiated, and operationalized, providing insights into the complexities of aligning public and private sector interests to enhance societal benefits in property-led planning.

Our findings demonstrate three key challenges within the social value creation process: mismatching expectations, changing authority, and missing communication. These challenges complicate the alignment of social value objectives throughout the project life cycle. By introducing a new lens for interpreting the intricate landscape of entrepreneurial governance, we highlight how conflicting public and private interests complicate the understanding of social value generated through property-led planning.

Currently, social value remains elusive due to its complex and dynamic nature, coupled with the absence of clearly defined parameters. Shaped by multiple actors with varying motivations across different stages, social value poses a challenge in its operationalization. While municipal planning entities theoretically hold the key to ensuring the continuity of social value creation throughout property development phases, market-driven urban development trends and entrepreneurial governance models constrain their effectiveness, resulting in a fragmented planning and regulatory landscape. This underscores the need for a more integrated approach, bridging between public and private sector interests to realize social value's full potential in property development.

Our arguments are based on extensive case study research of four major property development projects in Amsterdam to meet the city's housing and sustainability ambitions. An analysis of local regulations shows that the municipality of Amsterdam has many social ambitions, but no firm definition of social value. Furthermore, the complex nature of the local administration and fragmented property development practices throughout the city leaves the municipality vulnerable to project-specific negotiations and compromises when it comes to achieving social ambition. In-depth interviews with actors involved in the four selected projects illuminate the challenges of translating social value into concrete outputs.

This article is structured as follows. First, we discuss the process and challenges of implementing social value in property on a theoretical level and present our framework of analysis consisting of three phases: perception, implementation, and operation. In the methodology section, we describe our research approach, methods of data collection, and analysis. Then, we contextualise planning for social value in Amsterdam. Against this

backdrop, we analyse how social value transforms from perception to practice, following our three-step analytical framework. Finally, we present our findings and conclusions.

Understanding social value as a value creation process in property-led planning

Social value is about the social impact of an individual, organisation, or project on its community and surroundings (Raiden & King, 2022). It is a mechanism to ensure the long-term social sustainability of the built environment by creating attractive places for individuals to live, work, and play – both now and in the future. Such places reflect local needs of existing and future residents, offer safety, inclusivity, good planning, management, equal opportunities, and high-quality services for all – contributing to a high quality of life (Dempsey et al., 2011). Social value involves leaving a lasting positive impact on communities long after the construction process is complete. This involves adding value throughout the lifecycle of a property, from design and procurement to construction, operation, and disposal, without making costs unaffordable (Bailey, 2022; Hatleskog, 2021; Raiden & King, 2022).

To gain a deeper understanding, we turn to social sustainability literature that provides diverse accounts of the various physical and non-physical outcomes of property development. This body of work emphasizes how these outcomes are connected to the creation of social value at every stage of a project's life cycle. Physical outcomes, such as the provision of affordable housing, resilient infrastructure, and accessible public spaces, directly contribute to social value by enhancing the quality of life and meeting the needs of diverse populations. Non-physical outcomes including social cohesion, community identity, and the promotion of well-being, further amplify this value by fostering strong social networks, a sense of place, and long-term community resilience. These outcomes, as outlined in studies like Shirazi et al. (2022) and Colantonio & Dixon (2011), are measured through a variety of qualitative and quantitative indicators (see Table 1). Reports, such as those from the UK Green Building Council, underscore the importance of integrating these considerations into the planning and development process to ensure that property developments not only meet immediate needs but also leave a lasting, positive impact on communities, thereby fulfilling the broader goals of social sustainability (Colantonio & Dixon, 2011; Shirazi et al., 2022) and social value (UKGBC, 2018).

Traditionally, social value has been associated with planning and public policy, often addressed through land value capture mechanisms. However, it extends beyond mere value capture mechanisms (Botticini et al., 2022). In urban planning, social value refers to the positive impacts and benefits that planning and policy initiatives bring to communities and society as a whole. It encompasses a wide range of factors that contribute to well-being, quality of life, and equity within urban areas. Social value is deeply intertwined with the concept of the public interest, as urban planning aims to serve the needs and aspirations of the public

and promote the common good. Similar to the public sector, the property industry identifies social value through social infrastructure, diverse housing types that accommodate different income levels, and social equality (PwC & ULI, 2021). It is a concept with both concrete and abstract dimensions. While physical attributes, such as public spaces, accessibility to transportation, or urban amenities, are easier to identify, non-physical aspects, such as community integration, well-being, and happiness, remain abstract (Council, 2018).

Table 1: Tangible and intangible outcomes of social sustainability (based on Colantonio & Dizon, 2011; Shirazi et al., 2020; UKGBC, 2018)

Tangible social outcomes of property development		
Housing and infrastructure	Accessibility and connectivity	Social and environmental considerations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing comfortable and affordable homes • Diverse building uses and tenures • Resilient buildings and infrastructure • Mixed land use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility to transportation, key urban amenities, high-quality public space • Neighborhood quality and density • Spatial pattern and connectivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limit resource use and waste • Socio-economic diversity
Intangible social outcomes of property development		
Socio-economic opportunities	Social fabric	Health and well-being
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thriving local businesses • Job opportunities for local people and vulnerable individuals • Promising industry for the workforce of the future • Supporting and growing local chains • Developing local skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrating community to surrounding area • Protecting social fabric from disruption • Thriving social networks • Strong local identity, distinctive character and culture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good physical and mental health • Feeling of safety and security • Sense of place and ownership • Participation and empowerment • Neighborhood and home quality satisfaction • Wellbeing, happiness and quality of life • Healthy air quality

Situating social value in the entrepreneurial urban governance context

The emergence of entrepreneurial forms of urban governance, in which municipalities collaborate closely with private sector actors in an opportunity-driven manner, influences the way social value is framed in spatial planning institutions. Financialization and property-led planning have brought property market and public planning actors closer, sparking critical inquiries into public accountability and social responsibilities (Tasan-Kok et al., 2020). This joint process of property development has raised questions about planning policies, which not only shape the developmental context but also establish the operational framework for property actors (Adams & Tiesdell, 2012), while also redistributing resources and linking them to the wider public interest. Discussions on social value and mechanisms of measuring social value creation within the property industry are gaining traction (Corfe & Pardoe, 2022; Robin, 2022). Yet, much critical planning literature still expresses dichotomous thinking: considering

the public sector as the proponent and the private sector as the opponent of the creation of social impact or benefits in urban development (Acioly Jr., 2001; Botticini et al., 2022; Boyne, 2001; Lyons et al., 2006).

A recent focus on social value within the property industry was triggered by growing awareness and pressures to evaluate the sustainability of property investments through the recognition of social responsibilities which led to the creation of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) standards (Brounen et al., 2021). While environmental and governance aspects were traditionally central in these evaluations, there has been a noticeable shift towards the 'S' in ESG recently. This growing attention offers a powerful means to disrupt traditional entrepreneurial governance models. It enables the co-creation of new built environments, actively involving a diverse range of stakeholders, and advancing wider sustainability agendas (Raiden & King, 2022).

Within planning theory and practice, the idea that urban development is a (social) value-creation process is not new (Murphy & Fox-Rogers, 2015). Instead, planning is known to encapsulate physical and non-physical attributes which create social value at various spatial scales (Vigar et al., 2020). However, the process of how social value is perceived, defined, and correspondingly translated into actual property development projects remains abstract, particularly considering the interdependencies between public and private actors in property development.

Translating these abstract characteristics, norms, and principles of a concrete project through the spatial regulatory framework requires exploring how social value is created through involved public and private actors. As we will demonstrate in this article, social value creation should be understood as a dynamic process, not as a static definition with fixed characteristics. This requires a frame of analysis to encapsulate this dynamism by breaking the value creation process down into several steps.

Social value creation process as a novel frame of analysis

A useful starting point for exploring social value is provided by Jain et al. (2020) who explore social value creation from a public administrative perspective. They argue that social value creation occurs through three means: i) identifying individual perspectives on social value through diverse perceptions; ii) implementation of these perceived ideals by individuals who drive the social value creation process through collaboration; and iii) the mobilization of resources to operationalize the social value creation process (Jain et al., 2020). These elements collectively form an ecosystem wherein shared values can be translated from setting to implementing.

We integrate these concepts into our framework to analyse social value creation within the property development process (see Figure 1). The property development process unfolds across three stages: area strategy, project acquisition, and project realization, aligning with

Figure 1: Urban planning process of property development projects

Adams and Tiesdell's (2012) notion of property development processes. It is important to understand the stages of property development as they are connected to the planning dynamics before delving deeper into the stages of the social value creation process. While there are overlaps between the property development and social value creation processes, they are not synchronised.

Area strategy represents the “framing” stage where policies are formulated in anticipation of future development, reflecting broader narratives of social value shaped by planners and policymakers. This stage is influenced by a wide range of factors such as social, demographic, political, or economic changes that create incentives, aspirations, and intentions to develop new projects or re-develop existing ones (Adams & Tiesdell, 2012). Next, project acquisition entails the “sourcing” of the project site, aligning closely with the values set in area strategies, while also considering development feasibility against regulations and market appeal. Upon land acquisition, project stakeholders identify “new” values and preferences (Auzins & Chigbu, 2021).

Insights from project management literature indicate that the initial phase in a project's development holds the highest potential for value creation through effective collaboration (Toukola et al., 2023). During this stage, project stakeholders negotiate to develop a shared understanding of project outcomes and a collective vision to ensure its success (Toukola et al., 2023). Finally, project realization involves the implementation stage encompassing (pre)construction and marketing efforts of the project, with the developer managing risks and balancing speed, cost, and quality (Adams & Tiesdell, 2012).

The planning process is dynamic. It comprises stages of exploration, visioning, zoning, implementation, and operation. The linkage between planning and property development stages varies contextually. For instance, in some cases, the area strategy is initiated during the

exploration stage of a plan-making process, and in other cases during the visioning stage. Sometimes project acquisition coincides with the visioning stage or occurs after the zoning plan is being produced. Creating a static depiction of this dynamic process is challenging. Hence, the stages of planning, project development, and social value creation are nested within each other like matryoshka dolls (Figure 1).

The perception phase of social value creation involves different interpretations of project stakeholders with different backgrounds leading to potential barriers in the implementation phase (Bowman & Thompson, 2009). Stakeholders often evaluate outcomes based on their own experiences and expectations, underscoring the importance of understanding their perceptions (Toukola et al., 2023). This phase incorporates aspects of development prospects and feasibility that Adams and Tiesdell (2012) address, by highlighting perceptions in planning regulations and local policies, including area strategies, and involving project actors themselves.

The implementation stage of social value creation incorporates Adams and Tiesdell's (2012) feasibility testing and negotiations between public and private sector actors until construction agreements are made and the project is realised. This stage is strongly influenced by these actors' collaboration as well as the resources they acquire to implement their social value objectives. Social value outputs in this phase are particularly made in terms of physical construction. Furthermore, to reflect contemporary property development practices in which investors are increasingly dominant, we expand Adams and Tiesdell's (2012) property development process model and add another phase, namely operation. Investors often remain involved in an area beyond the completion of a project, for instance through property management. Thus, the operation phase refers to the maintenance of a project that has been completed at a physical level. This operation highlights the continuous involvement of actors in a completed project and is particularly connected to more intangible social value outcomes.

It is important to note that the three phases do not always occur in a perfectly linear manner as shown in Figure 1. Social value perceptions can change during a property development project, and new ambitions and targets can emerge during the implementation or operation. Nonetheless, this framework allows us to understand how and why some social values travel through from the perception phase until the operation phase, while others get lost. Furthermore, while the public sector is mostly understood as a 'mobilizer' of social value (Souitaris & Zerbinati, 2005), our framework tracks the changing influence of public and private actors throughout the property development process, examining the translation of social value as the outcome of an intricate public and private sector interplay.

Methodology

Our empirical research consists of two levels of analysis. It begins by examining Amsterdam's planning and development context as it strives to integrate social value amidst institutional

complexities. Building upon the insights of van Dijk & van der Vlist (2015) and Adams and Tiesdell (2010), we contend that governments play a dual role in actively shaping and co-creating markets and by fostering collaboration with various stakeholders to establish and achieve shared objectives (Mazzucato, 2023). We thus initially explore the extent to which the institutional context curates a foundation for social value creation. Specifically, by examining how rules, regulations and norms shaped by planning practices, subsequently impact social value in property development. This entails describing the influence of factors such as land ownership, regulations, and policy visions on shaping the dynamics of social value creation in property development.

We selected four projects that contain numerous examples of how social value targets get lost in translation between property development and urban planning processes: The Valley in Zuidas, Amsterdam Vertical in Sloterdijk, Het Dok in NDSM-Werf, and Our Domain in Zuidoost. All four projects are within the city's investment hotspots, attracting developers, and local and international investors, and are simultaneously key areas for the municipality to achieve their housing objectives. The projects were selected based on their sustainability marketing and size relative to the surrounding area. We set out to analyze the four projects by connecting them to existing regulations and creating actor maps which served as a starting point for our interview requests.

The second part of our analysis delves into actors' perceptions of social value and its translation into property development processes. Recognizing that individual actions can have broader societal implications, thus affecting social value creation (Jain et al., 2020), we emphasize the importance of understanding diverse perspectives on value (Toukola et al., 2023). Based on this understanding we conducted a total of 16 interviews with key stakeholders, including high-profile municipal and property actors directly and indirectly involved in four different projects within Amsterdam. Ten interviews were held with planners and municipal advisors on city-wide policy and governance arrangements to unpack the underlying connections between the political environment, regulatory context, and their practical implications on the social value creation process. Among the ten public sector interviewees, we spoke with four project managers from the Project Management Bureau overseeing day-to-day operations of the case studies, a researcher from Data and Statistics (*Data en Onderzoek*) involved in housing research and policy advice, and Chief Planner at the Spatial Planning and Sustainability (*Ruimte en Duurzaamheid*) department who was closely involved in the development of Amsterdam's Environmental Vision 2050.

The remaining six interviews were conducted with project developers and investors directly related to our case studies. We requested elaboration on their experiences within the regulatory context and their perceptions of social value, particularly in relation to how these values are mobilized into projects. We aimed to understand the challenges faced on a day-to-

day basis dealing with complex regulations, their influence on decision-making processes, and how they relate to the progression of social value.

Upon completion, all interviews were transcribed from which we conducted a content analysis to identify themes and relationships between actors' perceptions and the social value creation process. To maintain the interviewees' anonymity, we are unable to provide further information on the interviewees' backgrounds or assign them to specific projects. Instead, we zoom out and try to present conclusions on the general processes taking place in all four projects.

Amsterdam's context of planning for social value

The goal of Dutch spatial planning is to promote spatial development that serves the well-being and prosperity of society (van Rooy et al., 2006). Historically, the Dutch planning landscape followed a predominantly planning-led approach until the 1960s. However, as the government faced challenges in meeting societal needs, there was a shift towards involving the private sector to achieve broader societal goals. This transition led to the Spatial Planning Policy (*De Nota Ruimte*) promoting area development, which decentralized power to local municipalities and highlighted their role in managing area projects (van Rooy et al., 2006). This more adaptable approach to planning granted municipalities greater autonomy in crafting plans and devising strategies. Consequently, area development became a shared responsibility among various stakeholders, including developers, investors, and municipal planners, fostering new avenues for collaboration with the property sector. Property organizations such as NEPROM work closely with local municipalities to deliver projects with high social and environmental value (NEPROM, 2023). Moreover, it is common for large investors to have a direct relationship with the municipality to discuss city development and investment opportunities (Interviewee 11).

The shift towards collaborative approaches in Dutch spatial planning underscores the evolving dynamics between municipalities and the property sector. However, this joint endeavour intersects with the complex reality of municipal governance, particularly in the case of Amsterdam where the municipality owns a majority of the land making it both a planner and market actor. This dual function, as described by van Dijk & van der Vlist (2015), creates an inherent tension. On one hand, the municipality acts as a regulator, setting rules and plans for public land use through democratic decision-making processes. On the other hand, it directly engages in the market by owning and managing land, functioning as a player on the field (van Dijk & van der Vlist, 2015). This interplay between regulatory control and active involvement in the market generates conflicts between social and economic interests. The municipality's actions in land acquisition and management may not always align with democratic processes, potentially skewing outcomes in favour of economic interests over

social considerations. This dual role complicates the integration of social value into effective policies.

In the last decade, Amsterdam has intensified its focus on sustainability goals through its latest initiative, the ‘Amsterdam Environmental Vision 2050’ (*Omgevingsvisie Amsterdam 2050*). It envisions transforming Amsterdam into a ‘Human Metropolis’ (*Een menselijke metropool*), steering the city’s growth towards greater equity, sustainability, and integration. Key goals include investing in infrastructure, facilities, green spaces, transitioning to more sustainable energy sources, and reducing waste (Amsterdam, 2021b). The vision outlines six ‘values’: the inclusive city, the sustainable city, the vital city, the healthy city, the liveable city and the compact city (*ibid.*). Specific action points include densification through 150.000 new apartments within the existing built-up area, enhancing public spaces and greenspaces, fostering an environment that encourages encounter and play, and promoting neighbourhood participation (*ibid.*).

The specific terminology of social value, however, is sparsely used in Amsterdam’s policies. It appears in the municipality’s procurement policy (Amsterdam, 2022b) and in the neighbourhood rights framework which encourages residents to bring forward initiatives that “*do have social value and are an improvement for the neighbourhood and its residents*” (Amsterdam, 2021a, p. 16). This is similar to the UK’s initial approach with the Social Value Act, however, in the UK, the act progressed into broader agendas, including urban planning and development. Amsterdam’s focus, however, remains confined to innovation and entrepreneurship. Since 2015, the municipality operates a programme called ‘Amsterdam Impact’, which focuses on supporting social entrepreneurs who “*create both financial and social value*” (*I amsterdam*, n.d.: para. 1). Additionally, it supports social entrepreneurs that prominently features the notion of social value in the core of their business model such as Social Enterprise NL (Amsterdam, 2019). This organization is a national membership body representing 390 Dutch social enterprises and seeks innovative solutions for social challenges (Verloop & Hillen, 2021). This highlights how social value discourses are particularly picked up in business-related situations.

A key conflict exists between the creation of (affordable) housing and sustainability ambitions. From a social sustainability standpoint, more concrete tools such as minimum requirements for social infrastructure provisions (such as health, education, sport, and green space facilities) exist, as well as requirements for including 40% social housing and 40% middle-income housing in new development projects (Interviewee 3). However, the former is criticised for using a “blueprint model” based on inner-city calculations disregarding neighbourhood-specific needs, and the latter for too much flexibility that allows for project-specific negotiations (Özogul, 2019), or developers’ ability to construct small student housing units to fulfil their social housing quota.

Ultimately, concrete planning decisions in Amsterdam often come down to the negotiations and collaboration between public and private sector actors in specific development projects (Tasan-Kok et al., 2019). Municipal interviewees have pointed out that the vision's ambitious goals often conflict, requiring project-specific choices to navigate competing priorities (Interviewee 5). Additionally, it was criticised that political ambitions such as the ones surrounding sustainability are incorporated into multiple policies but tend to lack “*an overarching goal*” (Interviewee 4). This fragmented governance landscape is characterized by divergent approaches to property developers (Özogul & Tasan-Kok, 2020). Planners struggle with the growing discrepancies between municipal policy ambitions on the one hand, and concrete property development practices “on the ground” (Özogul, 2021). Nonetheless, as the following analysis shows, there are overlaps between social value understandings between the municipality and private actors in property development.

The translation process of social value in property development to planning

The translation of social value outcomes from perception to implementation and operation proved to be quite complex. Our analysis underscores the evolving dynamics between municipal and property actors throughout the property development projects. We find that the translation process of social value in property development to planning gets lost due to conflicting and overlapping perceptions; changing authority and difficulties in translating policy goals into project goals in the implementation phase; and missing communication between public and private sectors to maintain social value in the operation phase. Efforts to address these challenges require collaboration, effective communication, and a clear regulatory framework as we demonstrate below.

Conflicting and overlapping perceptions of social value

The various perceptions surrounding built environments are interconnected, pointing towards a shared desire for people-centric, well-connected, mixed-use, and sustainable spaces. Both public and private entities share this vision, albeit for different reasons. However, the challenge lies in the differing approaches to realizing these values. Rather than co-creating them, values tend to be defined individually based on organizational objectives and zoning ordinances, often becoming diluted into mere “requirements”. This disconnect persists due to the evolving nature of the development process, where the municipality's role shifts, placing greater responsibility on short-term players like developers. When regulations and policies define the “rules of the game”, complexities and contradictions arise, weakening the foundation for upholding social values throughout the development process. Ultimately, feasibility constraints often hinder the full translation and maintenance of social value from conception to completion.

The analysis of the four case study projects examined the perceptions of municipal actors, developers, and investors, on social value at different levels. Figure 2 presents a comprehensive overview revealing similarities and differences between municipal and property actors in their conceptualizations of social value, and their focus on different scales. Municipal actors offered varied accounts of social value from all levels but mainly focussed on broader values related to creating a mixed social fabric and safe, high-quality built environment. Similarly, these factors were significant to property actors; however, their main interest centred around residents' satisfaction with their living environment which was associated with building a sense of community and ownership within their living environment. A total of 30 tangible and intangible values were articulated, the majority of which were tangible values. The key dimensions of social value expressed in the projects included green spaces, mixed programming, impact on surrounding areas, social diversity, and prioritizing local businesses.

Figure 2: Municipal and property actors' perceptions of social value

Municipal actors provided vastly different explanations of what social value is. One interviewee, for instance, classified social value as “*all the values except the financial value to put it simply*” (Interviewee 5), exhibiting an unconscious separation from the perceived finance-driven objectives of property actors. Social value was seen as being created through two main domains: program and quality. The availability of mixed housing types was a key aspect of the program, as it would promote diversity among residents. Social facilities and shared living areas within the building were also important to serve both building and community residents, as seen in the Our Domain and Amsterdam Vertical projects. Commercial spaces were required in some projects, such as The Valley, Our Domain, and Het Dok, to connect the project with its surroundings. However, social housing or student housing was only included in Het Dok and Our Domain.

The second and most important factor mentioned by municipal actors was the quality of housing and surrounding urban areas. As expressed by one of the interviewees: “*Quality and the availability of social housing is one of these social services which you need to provide for some groups which are in need for social housing, but also to provide a good or appropriate quality of the surrounding areas of these dwellings*” (Interviewee 6). The expression of quality was often associated with the outcomes of the feeling of happiness, safety, and connection, resulting from building aesthetics, high-quality green spaces, and housing. Municipal actors’ narratives revealed varied accounts of social value that *could* result from program and quality. However, one interviewee suggested an alternative narrative about what *should be* done, citing the negative impact of the Het Dok project on neighbouring communities. The solution was to create a more inclusive program where neighbouring communities were given priority for housing within the development, as done in the Our Domain project.

Property actors shared similar narratives to municipal actors, however, they pertained to more project-specific perceptions of social value. The common (mis)conception of property actors is their lack of interest in engaging with intangible value creation. Yet, interviewees displayed quite the contrary. Perceptions of social value stemmed from personal understandings and organizational priorities. For instance, Interviewee 11 described how their company established a Social Impact Fund to achieve social targets within their ESG framework, aligning with their broader vision of creating inclusive and vital cities.

Many property actors stressed the importance of better understanding the needs and expectations of future target residents in creating a desirable living environment. For example, Interviewee 10 described: “*We did a sort of data sourcing, to ask thousands of people what kind of apartments you would like to see there [...] and what we tried to do is to make the layout of the building and the apartments in a way that those target groups could be very well facilitated*”.

Deducing from discussions with property actors, the desirability of the property was critical for the property itself and future developments. As Interviewee 8 narrated “[...] *everything that our on-site teams experience in operating our buildings, on how our residents value the buildings, what they like, don’t like, or miss - we get that feedback from the on-site teams and in every new project we do, we try to incorporate as much as possible of that feedback to try to make every single new project slightly better than the one before*”. Households’ level of satisfaction thus indicates the impact of the property on residents. This not only enables property actors to track down changing needs and behaviour but also to build connections with residents by creating direct communication channels.

In many instances, there was an overlap between municipal and property actor narratives when describing social value. For instance, in terms of the need for amenities, housing affordability, and public familiarity were indications that both municipal and property actors were dependent on each other to achieve a desirable environment. Property actors were thus

keen on working closely with the municipality to ensure social attributes were translated into the built environment. Simultaneously creating a similar environment within the project itself. In the projects of Amsterdam Vertical and Our Domain, social spaces were considered significant attributes of the building.

Shifting authority and challenges of translating policy goals into project goals in social value implementation

In the implementation phase, plans and agreements between municipal and property actors are put into action. However, several factors from an institutional and project level influence the direction of development actions. These are mainly the complex regulatory environment and the changing role of public and private actors within the process. Amsterdam is known for its complex regulatory environment which is shaped by regulations and policies at national, provincial, and local levels. These are classified into two types: hard and soft policies. Hard policies which are essentially regulations define obligatory infrastructure activities, building construction, environmental activities, and zoning requirements; and soft policies which are broader principles that guide actions and decision-making. As we have illustrated in the previous section, Amsterdam sets high ambitions for its urban development context. In our interviews with public officials and private actors, they emphasized the significance of the Environmental Vision 2050 which encompasses both types of policy making.

In the implementation phase, the developer assumes an active role in project realization, including the management of stakeholders, project costs, timelines, quality, and potential risks. The planner takes on a supporting role focusing on whether the project is developed according to specified plans and regulations; coordinating with other municipal departments such as public space and transportation to ensure adequate infrastructure for the project; communicating with residents and businesses to inform them of the project's progress and address any concerns that may arise.

Our analysis illustrates two underlying factors that influence social value implementation: the changing role of public and private actors within the process, and the regulatory environment that facilitates social value creation. Figure 3 illustrates the changing influence of project actors within the different phases of the projects' realization. Contrary to the planning phase where the municipality holds a higher level of authority, the status shifts towards the developer, who orchestrates the process and is entrusted with translating goals set in the planning phase into implementation (Figure 3).

Developers have a short-term presence in the property development process. Our analysis showed that motivation to pursue social value creation was dependent on internal drivers, such as the extent to which their organization is value-driven. For example, one developer stated: *Our founder [...] had the idea that he would always like to create better, more healthy and more sustainable buildings to, you know, to create a better environment around us and*

be an example for occupiers and investors, that buildings could still be beautiful, could still be used the way they would like to use it, but can be sustainable, and as a developer, you can earn money with it” (Interviewee 9). Alternatively, external drivers also play a significant role. Another developer mentioned that despite their interest in pursuing sustainability goals, it was dependent on external influences, specifically municipal and investor requirements (Interviewee 10).

Figure 3: Role of actors in different project development phases

The emphasis on Amsterdam’s sustainability-driven regulatory context, particularly highlighted by Amsterdam’s Environmental Vision 2050 (*Omgevingsvisie Amsterdam 2050*) underscores the municipality’s commitment to long-term environmental and social objectives. This vision derived from the Environmental Act integrates social and environmental considerations into the city’s spatial development (Amsterdam, 2021b). However, while the municipality’s regulatory framework sets ambitious goals, navigating the complex landscape of policies poses significant challenges. One interviewee noted: “[...] there are so many ambitions in Urban Vision or anywhere, it’s very hard to obey all these ambitions. And it’s also very hard to check if all the project leaders are obeying all these ambitions. So, you always have to make priorities on this” (Interviewee 5).

Amsterdam has a rigorous policymaking landscape comprising both strict, enforceable regulations (hard policies) and broader guiding principles (soft policies). These policies collectively shape various aspects of governance and decision-making in the city, covering areas such as infrastructure, construction, environmental activities, and zoning regulations. Navigating between the different policies proved to be challenging particularly given how policy documents are loosely framed. For instance, the municipality provides reference standards for social infrastructure and public spaces (*Amsterdamse referentienorm voor maatschappelijke voorzieningen, groen en speelruimte*) acknowledging that “the values for a liveable, complete city are a high-quality level of facilities”. It further states that “the reference standards are dynamic in nature because they are based on policy or an

extrapolation of what is present in Amsterdam” (Gemeente Amsterdam, 2018, p. 5, *translated*). The implementation of these standards is thus left to the discretion of project managers.

Meeting the demands of municipality requirements is often perceived as excessive by developers. Particularly in Amsterdam, local requirements exceed those set at a national level, leading to negotiation processes characterized by compromises and trade-offs to achieve mutually beneficial outcomes. Interviewee 11 described: *“The municipality always has too many demands on new real estate projects, they wanted it to be sustainable, cheap, have parking under the ground, and want a high ground price [...] and it’s always a negotiation between the developer and the municipality to see what choice you make in a project and how you make it feasible.”*

However, property actors also benefit from widely set visions. In the pre-planning phase when acquiring a project, developers seemed to ‘overpromise’ by presenting an exceptional project vision that goes beyond municipal requirements. As one municipal project manager noted *“[...] after the tender, the most difficult thing was to deal with the developer to make sure that they commit to what they promised [...] because it’s a big difference, to win the tender and have a beautiful plan. But then to realize it and make sure the plan is going to be realized as the developer promised.”* (Interviewee 7).

This challenge is compounded by fading municipal influence during the project’s execution, making it difficult to maintain the original value-creation goals. Interviewee 7 continued to explain: *“It was very difficult because it wasn’t always possible for them to make the plan as they promised because it was too expensive, and they had all kinds of problems [...] and they did make some changes in the project, the big houses were changed to smaller houses.”* It nuances that in navigating these complexities, developers strive to balance the demands of public stakeholders while ensuring the feasibility and realization of their project visions.

Missing communication between public and private sector to maintain social value in the operation phase

One of the major challenges in maintaining value creation in the operation phase is the changing role of the municipality within the property development process. The wider regulatory landscape provides better insights into how the municipality of Amsterdam operationalises social value. In this respect, it is important to know that the local administration of Amsterdam is a vast public-sector organisation that employs almost 18.000 civil servants (Amsterdam, 2021c) divided into five clusters: economic services, social services, community services, public space management, and operational services (Amsterdam, 2022a), which encompass various departments and City agencies. Municipal project managers are embedded across different departments, especially in the ‘Space and Sustainability’ and

'Land and Development' departments, and the 'Project Management Office' which is responsible for planning and administering large-scale property development projects. Furthermore, there is a separate 'Housing' department which is of growing importance due to Amsterdam's ambition to build 7500 new apartments every year (Amsterdam, 2020). This complex setup creates inconsistencies and divergent policy approaches to property development and developers (Özogul, 2021), even though efforts are made to enhance cross-divisional collaboration (Taşan-Kok & Özogul, 2021; Interviewee 2).

Similar to developers, municipal project managers operate on a project-specific basis, thus concluding their role upon completion of a project. Even though the municipality continues to have an active presence through a separate department, the primary stakeholders involved in the initial planning phase are no longer present. Therefore, we account for this as the municipality being passive due to its changing role. At this point, the municipality's responsibility lies in managing and monitoring through different departments such as City Management (*Stadsbeheer*), which oversees the daily management, supervision, and safety of the city's public space. (Amsterdam, 2022a). Additionally, each district has its day-to-day management and a district committee comprised of neighborhood representatives, advising the executive board on the neighbourhood's situation (Amsterdam, 2016).

In parallel, the municipality's 'Living' (*Wonen*) research department continuously monitors changes and developments in areas to assess their liveability and develop the right policies for the housing market in Amsterdam (Interviewee 6). This is accomplished primarily through bi-annual surveys as a main tool to collect data on residents' perceptions of the area to assess "[...] *the housing market composition and development* [...]" as well as "[...] *the quality of housing and the quality of the living environment* [...]" (ibid). Looking into these assessments we found that the liveability study provides an overview of migration dynamics, area demographics, socio-economic standards, and overall quality of living. As for the housing assessment, it outlines housing market segments and income groups in Amsterdam, identifying changes in income distribution and the housing stock suitable to accommodate different income groups. These assessments provide an outlook on the current situation of areas to ensure "*the right policy on the overall housing market in Amsterdam is created*" and to check if "*something is wrong with the quality of that surroundings according to the answers given in our survey, then they have a signal that something is needed at some places in the city*" (Interviewee 6). These assessments provide insights into the development of an area but fail to provide an in-depth understanding of what people value, why, and to what extent.

Investors track urban area developments using similar insights. However, they focus on user satisfaction and residents' perceptions of their dwellings to identify market opportunities and gain valuable insights into their client base. Investors typically look for investments with long-term benefits and have recently turned their attention to properties that can have a

positive social impact: *“In the last three years we only buy (property) that is better than the environmental regulation. Now in 2022, the ‘social’ gets important. And we are looking at how to include that and how to measure it.”* (Interviewee 11). The growing importance of monitoring has thus led investors to develop their surveying methods to better inform decision-making: *“Everything that our on-site teams experience in operating our buildings: how our residents value the buildings, what they like, what they don’t like, or miss, etc. We get that feedback and in every new project we do, we try to incorporate (it) as much as possible”* (Interviewee 8). Unfortunately, efforts remain on a case-to-case basis depending on the extent of the organization’s interest and the holding period of an investment.

A crucial aspect of our analysis was to understand how social value outcomes determined in the initial phase were carried through once a project was complete. Interviews with planners shed light on the challenges they face describing the process as vague and difficult: *“In general, it’s quite simple to achieve ambitions which are in the building process, and it becomes harder to achieve when it comes to the years after the building.”* (Interviewee 5). Another interviewee described that concerns tended to revolve around adhering to use regulations, i.e. whether the property is being *“used in the right way”* (Interviewee 6). This form of monitoring is often dependent on municipal actors having a direct relationship with property owners or receiving concerns from other residents.

Discussion and findings

This article conducts a thorough analysis of social value from perception to practice within the planning domain highlighting the challenges involved in translating social value outcomes in property development amidst a complex institutional landscape. We argue that institutional fragmentation frequently impedes the effective harnessing of social value as it hinders its capture across municipal and property development practices.

We first analyze how Amsterdam’s entrepreneurial context challenges property developers and municipal actors to develop clear mechanisms to collaborate and prioritize a value creation process. While enabling mechanisms such as Amsterdam’s Environmental Vision set broad social and environmental sustainability criteria, these criteria are limited to ‘visions’ rather than enforceable standards, subject to market-driven decision making.

To address the complex nature of social value, we developed a framework to trace the value creation process through three stages: perception, implementation, and operation. The framework traces how social value is perceived, the formulation of project-related strategies throughout the realisation and maintenance at each project stage. We analyzed four case studies in Amsterdam – Het Dok, Valley, Our Domain, and Amsterdam Vertical – to understand how planners, developers, and investors conceptualize and implement social value objectives.

Our findings demonstrate that public and private actors face challenges aligning their expectations at each stage of the property development process. These challenges stem from three main issues: Conflicting and overlapping perceptions of social value, shifting authority during the implementation phase, and missing communication between public and private sector actors in the operation phase.

During the perception phase, both municipal and property actors described social value as creating people-centric, well-connected, sustainable places. These fall in line with the social sustainability standards outlined in the literature (see Table 1) and those reflected in the municipality's environmental vision. Perceptions stemmed from personal values, consumer expectations, organizational values, market demands, policies, and regulations. Both groups portrayed a clear understanding of social value and recognized its long-term importance. The main difference of their portrayal of social value was from difference levels. Municipal actors expressed it from a city and neighborhood level, while property actors more from a project level. Key challenges arise as development feasibility and regulatory requirements offset the translation of social value objectives into practice.

In the implementation phase, ideological interpretations often faltered due to a lack of regulation on social value and the changing roles of actors. A key issue was the diminishing role of municipal project managers as developers took over project management. The short-term focus of developers and the prioritization of feasibility and requirements created obstacles to maintaining social value objectives, which often depended on the proactive efforts of property actors. At present, environmental goals have been regulated by national and local governments, thus setting clear frameworks and strategies for their mobilization. However, social goals are unclearly defined and regulated, making it more challenging to ensure that they are consistently prioritized and pursued in development projects and other initiatives. Thus, levelling the prioritization of environmental and social ambitions also becomes essential.

In the operation phase, we observed a disconnect between those who set social value objectives in the perception phase and those responsible for maintaining them in the operation phase. Responsibilities shift, and monitoring processes are often unclear and inconsistent, leading to difficulties in sustaining social value due to mismatched expectations and communication gaps.

The loss of social value is not primarily due to its ambiguity, lack of interest among actors, nor due to inadequate measurement tools. Instead, the main issues are in the shifting influence and motivations of key actors as processes become increasingly complex. As a result, ensuring consistent prioritization of social value becomes challenging. Moreover, the unregulated nature of social value means that it may not often receive the same priority as other factors such as financial gain, contributing to an unstable and ambiguous process of value creation.

Conclusion

Social value creation can be an innovative mechanism to reshape property development processes. As the property sector strives to meet its ESG goals and the public sector in achieving its sustainability visions, mobilizing social value can be a useful avenue for transforming processes, disseminating best practices, and altering existing relationships. However, under the current context of entrepreneurial urban governance, mobilizing social value proves challenging due to the dynamic and multifaceted nature of property development processes. Yet, this complexity presents an opportunity for planners to actively create avenues for engagement and for property actors to collaborate more effectively to achieve their social targets.

This paper posits that the public sector needs to adopt a more prominent role in mobilizing social value throughout the property development process. This entails several critical actions: first, gaining a comprehensive understanding of how various stakeholders perceive social value; second, effectively integrating social value objectives into planning and development phases; and third, establishing robust mechanisms for the sustained monitoring and maintenance of social value outcomes post-completion. Moreover, the public sector should actively facilitate collaboration between public and private actors to ensure that social value objectives are not overshadowed by financial imperatives.

Dialogue among property owners and developers serves as a valuable mechanism for knowledge exchange, capacity building, and awareness raising within the property industry. However, a significant barrier to achieving successful dialogues lies in agreeing on more ambitious goals beyond regulatory minimums. To foster effective dialogue, stakeholders must commit to collectively achievable objectives, with the public sector guiding these discussions to align the pursuit of social value with broader public goals. While critical analyses of property markets often oversimplify development processes (Özogul & Tasan-Kok, 2020), acknowledging the complexity of factors influencing outcomes is crucial (Robin, 2022; Elsmore, 2020; Muñoz Gielen & Lenferink, 2018; Weber, 2002). By recognizing the multifaceted nature of property development (Campbell et al., 2014), including the influence of investors alongside planners and developers, we can better navigate the complexities of the field and address emerging trends such as ESG and responsible investment. Failure to adopt this multidimensional perspective risks overlooking opportunities for intervention and positive change in the property industry.

Municipal project managers have access to resources such as information, decision-making power, and the ability to influence the built environment, holding a unique position of authority. Given the right conditions, they can balance their responsibilities towards their clients and their duty to serve the broader public interest (Adams & Tiesdell, 2012). However, municipal project managers are constrained by limited roles, reducing their influence to a 'box-ticking' approach which undoubtedly puts the pursuit of social value at risk (Parker et al.,

2020). Hartley (2005) recognizes that value creation can occur top-down, such as the Amsterdam Environmental Vision 2050; bottom-up, exemplified by organizations like Amsterdam Impact and Social Enterprise NL; and laterally, through the adoption of best practices by public/project managers. Yet, lateral processes are often locked into “business as usual” despite policy frameworks that provide opportunities for change.

Another important aspect is the strategic use of diverse information channels to enhance operational management as starting points for mobilizing social value creation. Local governments have established methods for knowledge collection, such as open data platforms and civic initiatives. Furthermore, they actively seek ways to connect with property markets to better understand market dynamics and trends. One effective strategy has been training civil servants in real estate to enhance their administrative capacity and deepen their expertise in the market (Stadszaken.nl, 2023).

In parallel, property market actors develop collaborative mechanisms, establishing intelligence channels that build market knowledge, trust, and connections between property actors and policymakers (Taşan-Kok, 2024). This form of governance places negotiation at the core of decision-making, where continuous dialogue between stakeholders becomes essential for aligning market interests with public objectives. Harnessing social value begins by recognizing values created and the potential values that can be unlocked. The changing actor landscape signals an opportunity for the public sector to significantly improve its operational management and decision-making processes, ultimately leading to more effective social value creation.

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